

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AWUKU-ANNIE****FIRST NAME: AUGUSTINE****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr Gulma****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 11%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 11 Pro)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. According to the Turabian Manual of Style, which of the following helps researchers describe their project in a sentence?

- I want to help people understand Z (Significance), so I am working on X (Topic) to find Y (Question).
- I am working on X (Topic) because I want to find out Y (Question) so that I can help others understand Z (Significance).¹**
- I want to find out Y (Question) by working on X (Topic) so that people can understand Z (Significance).

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Ninth edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 20.

- Others can understand Z (Significance) if I find out Y (Question) by working on X (Topic).
2. Which of the following is not part of the structure of a regular essay?
- Overview.**²
- Introduction.
- Body.
- Conclusion.
3. Plagiarism is a grave offence in academia. Identify a non-plagiarised act among the following?
- Quoting an author with due acknowledgement.**³
- Paraphrasing without acknowledgement.
- Have someone write a paper for you and present it with your name on it.
- Copying from the internet without acknowledgement.
4. What can the Turabian Style also be referred to as?
- MLA Style.
- APA Style.
- Chicago Style.**⁴

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2024), 10.

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 34.

⁴ Turabian, 141.

- Havard Style.
5. The purposes of a dissertation concept paper include the following except one. Identify the odd one.
- What might be studied in the dissertation?
- Why does what might be studied in the dissertation need to be studied?
- How might what might be studied in the dissertation be studied?
- An abstract of the dissertation.**⁵
6. Which of the following is not true about the research problem?
- It is presented in one paragraph based on a critical literature analysis.
- It is concerned with content gaps in prior research.
- It is concerned with problems inherent in prior research methods.
- It is not the basis for the dissertation research.**⁶
7. Identify the two most common forms of citations as detailed in the Turabian Style.
- Notes-bibliography style and Author-notes style.
- Author-date style and Notes-bibliography style.**⁷
- Author-notes style and Author date style.
- Author-bibliography style and notes-bibliography style.

⁵ James Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 2.

⁶ Sampson, 28.

⁷ Turabian, 141.

8. The Turabian Style specifically mentions the reliable authority (dictionary) for spelling. Which of the following dictionaries is that authority?
- Oxford's English Dictionary on Lexicon.
 - Collins English Dictionary.
 - Merriam-Webster's Collegiate Dictionary.**⁸
 - Dictionary of Contemporary English.
9. What does the word *draft* about the EU legislation denote?
- That the Commission has formally approved the act in question.
 - That the act in question will not be formally approved by the Commission.
 - That the act in question has not yet been formally approved by the Commission.**⁹
 - That the act in question will undoubtedly be approved by the Commission.
10. What type of English dictionary is recommended for usage within the EU setting?
- Oxford's English Dictionary on Lexicon.**¹⁰
 - Collins English Dictionary.
 - Merriam-Webster's Collegiate Dictionary.
 - Dictionary of Contemporary English.

⁸ Turabian, 302.

⁹ European Union, "English Style Guide : A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission" (European Union, January 6, 2021), 78.

¹⁰ European Union, 17.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.